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Organic carbon sequestration potential of Slovenian agricultural soil and the impact of management practices on SOC stock

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ABSTRACT

Improving soil management is crucial for mitigating climate change by increasing soil organic carbon (SOC). This study addresses the question of whether Slovenian agricultural soils can increase SOC stocks and achieve the 4per1000 initiative (4p1000.org). We calculated the SOC stocks, soil carbon sequestration (SCS) potential of the fine soil fraction (<math><20\mu\text{m}</math>) (C_{sd}) and the SCS potential of bulk soil for different agricultural uses in Slovenia. In addition, we conducted agricultural land management scenarios to determine a possible increase in SOC stocks. The results showed an average SOC stock of 94.7 t ha^{-1} in the agricultural soils of Slovenia. High C_{sd} values were mainly found in croplands, intensive orchards and vineyards. The C_{sd} (0–30 cm) amounts to 16.3 Mt SOC for the entire country. In addition, our results on SCS potential were compared with similar assessments from other European countries, where the range of bulk soil SCS potential was between 0.03 and 2.8‰ SOC change yr^{-1} . With the current management of agricultural land in Slovenia, the SCS is almost balanced (+0.1‰). Different management scenarios showed that efficient fertilizer use, no-till, vegetation cover with biodiverse crop rotation and keeping residues on the surface lead to a significant SOC stock increase by 19.6 t ha^{-1} in 20 years, which supports the 4per1000 initiative target (10.5‰).

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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1. Introduction

One approach to mitigate the effects of climate change in the future will be better soil management. Large amounts of organic carbon (C) are present in the soil, and their preservation or even increase through sequestration of carbon from the atmosphere could reduce atmospheric carbon concentrations (Conant et al., 2001). Sequestration in soil is achieved by increasing the net flux of carbon from

the atmosphere to the soil environment, that is, by increasing the storage of carbon from primary production or by reducing the decomposition of organic matter (Smith, 2005). Models have been developed to calculate the potential of soils to sequester organic carbon (Chen et al., 2018a). Organic carbon sequestration in cultivated land is a slow process that can take many years. According to the results of Minasny et al. (2017), the rate of C sequestration in cropland is in the range of 0.03–1.00 t C ha⁻¹yr⁻¹. This range

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is wide because of the different climatic conditions and agrotechnical measures applied to agricultural soils. It is very important that sequestered soil organic carbon (SOC) remains in the soil for as long as possible. Soil organic matter stabilization occurs through aggregation and associated physical protection in structural aggregates (labile pool) and interaction with the mineral fraction (passive pool) (Hassink, 1997; Minasny et al., 2017; Poeplau et al., 2018). It is assumed that the fine mineral fraction ($\leq 20\mu\text{m}$) of the soil can protect SOC from (especially microbial) degradation and mineralization (Gregorich et al., 2006; Hassink, 1997; Poeplau et al., 2018). Based on this assumption, the concept of soil C saturation deficit (C_{sd} in t C ha^{-1}) was defined as the difference between the maximum possible organic C content in the fine fraction (C_{sat}) (Hassink, 1997) and the determined current SOC in the fine fraction (C_{fine}). Hassink's C_{sat} concept has also been criticized. Furthermore, the amount of SOC associated with sand particles accounted for a significant proportion of the total SOC stock. Wiesmeier et al. (2014) reported that the SOC associated with a fraction $>20\mu\text{m}$ is highly variable, accounting on average for approximately 60% and 40% of the total SOC in Bavarian forests and grassland soil surface layers, respectively. Numerous other studies have reported significant ($>20\%$) contributions of $>20\mu\text{m}$ SOC to total SOC in agricultural soils in temperate climates (Balesdent et al., 1998; Besnard et al., 2001). In addition, several authors have found that the increase in SOC stocks following a change in land management is largely due to an increase in the amount of organic matter in the sand fraction (e.g. Cardinael et al., 2015; Chimento et al., 2016; Feng et al., 2014). Therefore, it is expected that a significant part of the increase in SOC stocks caused by the implementation of agrotechnical measures to increase soil carbon stocks (e.g. conservation agriculture) will initially occur mainly in soil fractions $>20\mu\text{m}$. It follows from the above findings that the actual storage potential of SOC in the whole soil is the sum of C_{sat} and the contribution of C to the size fraction $>20\mu\text{m}$ ('particulate C').

Increasing soil organic carbon stocks can partially offset anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions (Lal, 2004; Paustian et al., 2016). Therefore, countries are encouraged in international negotiation mechanisms to consider agricultural soil management systems to account for CO_2 fluxes in terrestrial systems (Decision 2011/2/CMP.7; Decision 2013/529). Soil carbon management is the basis of the 4per1000 initiative, which is a voluntary action plan under the Lima-Paris Action Agenda to ensure food security and mitigate climate

change by increasing soil carbon stocks (<https://www.4p1000.org/>). Under this initiative, all partners are encouraged to implement programs with agricultural practices known to increase soil carbon stocks, such as organic farming, agroforestry, and conservation agriculture (Chimento et al., 2016; Lal, 2016; Minasny et al., 2017; Paustian et al., 2016). Rodrigues et al. (2021) assessed the potential for C sequestration in agricultural soils in 24 European countries (this assessment has not yet been published for Slovenia). Due to the different environmental conditions in the individual countries and the different agricultural practices, there is a wide range between countries. However, none of the countries would reach the 4per1000 target with current practices, which means that many additional measures would need to be researched and implemented (Rodrigues et al., 2021). In line with this initiative, policymakers have posed operational questions to the scientific community: What is the potential for carbon (CO_2) storage in soil? Is it possible to measure/estimate and map this storage potential at different spatial scales, from field to country, continent, or globally for the whole world? Which soil management techniques are most suitable, and how long will it take to reach this potential?

Our aim was to assess the state of SOC stocks in different agricultural land-use soils in Slovenia and to calculate the potential for SOC sequestration in a fine soil fraction ($<20\mu\text{m}$). Because we have the largest agricultural area in Slovenia, which is used as grassland and cropland, we were also interested in how the potential is influenced by clay content and soil depth. In addition to the sequestration of organic carbon in the fine fraction, we were also interested in the SOC sequestration potential of the total SOC, and not only the SOC associated with the fine fraction. For this purpose, we calculated the C sequestration potential using the IPCC Tier 1 method (IPCC, 2006). Using this method, we performed different agricultural land management scenarios for a possible increase in SOC stocks in Slovenian agricultural soils and compared them with the 4per1000 initiative.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Soil SOC stock determination by different land uses

Soil sampling was conducted from 2016 to 2020 at 330 sampling sites on behalf of the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food (MAFF). Detailed information on soil sampling can be found in the [Supplementary Material and Tables S1 and S2](#).

Table 1. Land uses and its short description included in the study.

Land use	Abb	Short description ^a
cropland	CR	annual and some perennial crops, cultivation
vineyard	VI	vines (<i>Vitis vinifera</i> L.)
intensive orchard	IO	fruit species, intensive
extensive orchard	EO	tall fruit trees, non-intensive
grassland	GR	grass, clover and forage plants, mowing or grazing
overgrown grassland	OG	young woody or thorny vegetation, 20–75% cover
land with trees and bushes	TB	trees and bushes, >75% cover

^aFor more information see [Supplementary material, Table S1](#).

Samples from shallower soils were excluded from the SCS sequestration potential at depth of 0–30 cm.

Samples were taken from different agricultural lands ([Table 1](#)). Prior to sampling, permission to collect soil samples was obtained from the landowners.

SOC stock was calculated from the measured SOC content and soil bulk density in samples from 0–10, 10–20 and 20–30 cm depth and then summed for 0–30 cm depth in each sampling site. It represents the SOC stock at the time of sampling (T0). For each land use the average SOC stock was calculated.

2.2. Fine soil fraction SOC deficit (Hassink's model)

Using the method developed by Hassink (1997) and supplemented by Chen et al. (2018a), which was applied to French soils, we calculated the organic C content in the fine soil fraction (<20 μm) (C_{fine} ; t ha⁻¹) for individual land uses and soil layers of 0–10 cm, 10–20 cm, and 20–30 cm. The SOC content in the fine fraction was calculated from the total SOC based on the study by Chen et al. (2018a), considering factor F, which represents the average proportion of organic carbon in the fine fraction of the soil in relation to the total organic carbon in the soil:

$$C_{fine} = SOC \times F [t ha^{-1}] \quad (1)$$

where SOC is soil organic carbon in a soil layer per ha (t ha⁻¹); F is 0.85 for cropland (CR), 0.69 for grassland (GR), 0.66 for overgrown grassland (OG), land with trees and bushes (TB) and 0.73 for other land uses, such as vineyard (VI), intensive (IO), and extensive orchard (EO), for depths of 0–30 cm (Chen et al., 2018a). Orchards and vineyards are categorized as other land uses for these factors because our permanent plantations are not fully cultivated; only one-third of the land is either cultivated or treated with herbicides.

Hassink (1997) created a model for the top 10 cm to calculate the saturation of the soil fine fraction (<20 μm) with SOC (C_{sat}), which is a non-labile and permanent form of SOC – mineral-associated SOC. The concept of soil C saturation deficit (C_{sd}) is defined as the difference between the maximum predicted content of organic C in the fine mineral fraction of the soil (C_{sat}) and the actual content of organic carbon in the fine fraction (C_{fine}). The C saturation in the fine fraction (<20 μm) (C_{sat}) was calculated for each land use and soil depth, according to Hassink (1997):

$$C_{sat} = 4,09 + 0,37 \times \% \text{ fine fraction } (<20 \mu\text{m}) \times BD [t ha^{-1}] \quad (2)$$

where C_{sat} is the C saturation (t ha⁻¹) in the upper 10 cm of the soil, the fine fraction is the content of soil particles <20 μm (%), and BD is the soil bulk density (t m⁻³).

The C saturation deficit (or excess; surplus) (t ha⁻¹) of the soil fine fraction (<20 μm) (C_{sd}) for each land use and depth was calculated as follows:

$$C_{sd} = C_{sat} - C_{fine} [t ha^{-1}] \quad (3)$$

where C_{sd} is the C saturation deficit (sequestration potential) of the soil fine fraction (t ha⁻¹), C_{sat} is the C saturation of the soil fine fraction (t ha⁻¹), and C_{fine} is the C of the fine fraction (t ha⁻¹).

The degree of C_{fine} of C saturation (%) was calculated by equation:

$$\%C_{sat} = C_{fine} / C_{sat} \times 100 [\%] \quad (4)$$

where $\%C_{sat}$ (%) is the percentage of saturation of C_{fine} in the fine fraction.

For the C sequestration potential of the fine fraction of the Slovenian agricultural land area, official statistical data (2019) for each agricultural land use were used (Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food [MAFF], 2019). In addition, data from the digital elevation model of the Surveying and Mapping Authority of the Republic of Slovenia was used to create a map of Slovenia (Surveying and Mapping Authority of the Republic of Slovenia [SMARS], 2017).

The statistical analysis was performed with R (package Rcmdr) version 4.0.3 (R Core Team, 2020). Homogeneity of variance was checked using Levene's test, and differences between land use, clay content and depth parameters were estimated using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) or the non-parametric version of ANOVA, the Kruskal-Wallis test at 0.05

level. To determine the differences between the treatments, the Tukey test was used after the ANOVA and the Dunn test with Bonferroni correction after the Kruskal-Wallis test.

2.3. Soil management scenarios of possible soil carbon sequestration (SCS) (IPCC Tier 1)

The SCS potential for Slovenia was calculated according to the guidelines of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2006, 2019). The calculations were based on the Tier 1 method for the warm-temperate-moist climate region that prevails in Slovenia (the majority of Slovenia's territory belongs to the ASL6 region according to Metzger et al. (2005)). Sequestration rates ($t\ C\ ha^{-1}yr^{-1}$) for CR, VI, and IO were calculated using the IPCC factors F_{LU} , F_{MG} and F_I (IPCC, 2019; Supplementary Material, Table S3) for cropland and perennial crops/tree crops, and the factors for grassland were used for EO, GR, and OG. The average SOC stock at 30 cm depth was used as the reference SOC stock, and the areas of each land use from the 2019 statistical data were considered (Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food [MAFF], 2019). The SCS potential was not calculated for TB because we assumed that the soil was already saturated for this land use.

The SCS potential rate ($t\ C\ ha^{-1}yr^{-1}$) was calculated for different scenarios in agriculture based on the IPCC factors and for each agricultural land use (depth up to 30 cm) (Supplementary material, Table S4 and Figure S1), taking into consideration different agricultural practices that could be implemented in Slovenian agriculture over 20 years, the IPCC default period, assuming no change in the land use category (e.g. conversion of cropland to grassland).

SCS calculations of management scenarios were made by following equations:

$$SOC_{(0+T)} = \sum (SOC_{(0)} \times F_{LU} \times F_{MG} \times F_I \times A) [tC] \quad (5)$$

where $SOC_{(0)}$ is the stock of organic carbon in mineral soils ($t\ C\ ha^{-1}$) determined in samples from 311 sampling points (SIST ISO 10694, 1995; SIST ISO 10693, 1996) and calculated from SOC content and bulk density (Supplementary material, Table S5). The IPCC factors considered (F_{LU} , F_{MG} , and F_I) are listed in Supplementary Material, Table S3. F_{LU} is the stock change factor for a given land use system, F_{MG} is the stock change factor for the management regime (e.g. tillage – estimated relative to the use of full tillage and nominal ('medium') carbon input levels), F_I is the

stock change factor for organic matter input, and A is the land area (ha).

The annual change in organic carbon stock in mineral soils was calculated as linear over a span of 20 years [Equation (6)]:

$$\Delta C_{\text{Mineral soil}} = (SOC_{(0+T)} - SOC_{(0)}) / D [tC\ yr^{-1}] \quad (6)$$

where $\Delta C_{\text{Mineral soil}}$ is the annual change in organic carbon stocks in mineral soils ($t\ C\ yr^{-1}$), $SOC_{(0)}$ is the soil organic carbon stock in the inventory period ($t\ C$) determined in samples from 311 sampling sites, $SOC_{(0+T)}$ is the soil organic carbon stock after 20 years of new soil management ($t\ C$), T is the number of years in a single inventory period, and D is the time dependence of the stock change factor, which is the standard period for the transition between equilibrium SOC values (years). In general, D is equal to 20 years, but depends on the assumptions made when calculating the F_{LU} , F_{MG} and F_I factors (IPCC, 2019). In our case, the inventory period was 20 years ($T=D=20$ years).

We predicted that overgrown grassland (OG) and land with trees and bushes (TB) will no longer show a linear annual increase in SOC stock, as they have already reached or are close to reaching equilibrium. TB areas have not been influenced by human activities for many years (at least 20–30 years); therefore, there is no soil disturbance. OG, which is overgrown with turf and young woody shrubs, has also been left to natural succession for at least 10 years, and therefore represents a transitional stage to TB. Both systems (TB and OG) had diverse vegetation types. Our hypothesis is that these lands represent the maximum achievable SCS potential in Slovenian agricultural soils and therefore serve as a reference. We assumed that actively farmed areas (cropland, grassland, orchards) are able to increase the SOC stock to the level of TB depending on the soil type (especially clay content). The maximum SOC stock can be achieved by changing agricultural land management technologies. We examined a 20-year linear increase in SOC stock according to different IPCC Tier 1 scenarios.

For each individual agricultural land use, we predicted a scenario in which soil management and the application of practices did not change over a period of 20 years (as usual; scenario 1, in CR numbered 1–3) (Figure 3). In addition, we have developed scenarios in which soil management can be adjusted or changed by introducing new practices (scenarios numbered 2 or more, in CR with 4 or 5). Descriptions of the individual land use scenarios can be found in the Supplementary Material, Figure S2.

Table 2. Average SOC stock, area of different land uses in Slovenia in 2019 and their C sequestration potential/deficit of fine fraction (C_{sd}) in $t\ ha^{-1}$ and Mt for 0–30 cm soil layer.

Land use	Land use area of total area of Slovenia		SOC stock $t\ ha^{-1}$	C_{sd}	
	Land use area ^a ha	%		$t\ ha^{-1}$	Mt
Cropland CR	179003	8.83	86.50	26.05	4.7
Vineyards VI	17880	0.88	66.70	65.26	1.2
Intensive orchards IO	4377	0.22	72.44	53.12	0.2
Extensive orchards EO	28081	1.39	92.93	24.31	0.7
Grassland GR	347223	17.13	97.43	26.75	9.3
Overgrown grassland OG	24543	1.21	100.77	18.46	0.5
Trees and bushes TB	33750	1.66	123.93	-7.53	-0.3
Total	634858	31.32	94.65	25.57	16.3
Total (no TB)	601108	29.66	93.01	27.43	16.6
Total (no OG, no TB)	576565	28.45	92.67	27.81	16.1

^aData: Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food (Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food [MAFF], 2019).

We elaborated seven different management scenarios considering different land-use scenarios for agricultural practices on CR, VI, IO, EO, GR, and OG, and calculated the SCS potential for Slovenia ($t\ C\ ha^{-1}$) over 20 years (Table 3).

3. Results

3.1. SOC stock of Slovenia

The average stock of organic C in the soil layer of 0–30 cm, calculated as the average of the total depth of the sampled soils of 0–10, 10–20 and 20–30 cm, is highest on TB ($123.9\ t\ ha^{-1}$), followed by OG ($100.8\ t\ ha^{-1}$), GR ($97.4\ t\ ha^{-1}$), EO ($92.9\ t\ ha^{-1}$) and CR ($86.5\ t\ ha^{-1}$) (Supplementary material, Table S4). Despite the additional input of organic matter to cropland with organic fertilizers, mineralization is accelerated by tillage (mouldboard plowing and additional soil bed preparation). VI ($66.7\ t\ ha^{-1}$) and IO ($72.4\ t\ ha^{-1}$) were characterized by a much lower SOC content. VI had the lowest SOC content because the vineyard areas were intensively cultivated, especially during planting, where deep plowing ($> 30\ cm$) was generally used and the inter-row strips were only partially vegetated. The strip between the individual vines is also treated with herbicides and is therefore not vegetated, which affects the SOC content. This explains the measured SOC values and their average, as the samples were taken as average samples across the vineyard, considering the inter-vine strip, herbicide strip, and tractor tracks. The same applies to IO.

According to the SOC of all different agricultural uses and considering the actual areas of individual land uses in Slovenia in 2019, the average SOC stock in the 0–30 cm layer is $94.7\ t\ ha^{-1}$ ($93.0\ t\ ha^{-1}$ if TB is not included) (Table 2). The SOC stocks for the individual soil layers are listed in Supplementary Material Table S4.

Table 3. SCS potential in 20 years ($t\ C\ ha^{-1}\ 20\ yr^{-1}$) and SCS potential rate in promile of SOC stock in Slovenia ($\%_o\ yr^{-1}$) for different agricultural management scenarios.

Management scenario	Land use scenarios	SCS potential ^a	p1000 ^b
		$t\ C\ ha^{-1}\ 20\ yr^{-1}$	$\%_o\ yr^{-1}$
1	CR1, VI1, IO1, EO1, GR1, OG1 <i>All land management unchanged (current practices)</i>	-9.07	-4.9
2	CR2, VI1, IO1, EO1, GR1, OG1 <i>as 1 only CR2 implemented (current practices)</i>	-5.70	-3.1
3	CR3, VI1, IO1, EO1, GR1, OG1 <i>as 1 only CR3 implemented (predominant current practices)</i>	0.17	0.1
4	CR3, VI2, IO2, EO2, GR1, OG1 <i>as 3 VI2, IO2, EO2 implemented</i>	2.11	1.1
5	CR4, VI2, IO2, EO2, GR1, OG1 <i>as 4 only CR4 implemented</i>	4.67	2.5
6	CR4, VI2, IO2, EO2, GR2, OG1 <i>as 5 only GR2 implemented</i>	19.61	10.5
7	CR5, VI2, IO2, EO2, GR2, OG1 <i>as 6 only CR5 implemented</i>	24.12	13.0

^aSOC change in 20 years of agricultural management scenario.

^bCalculation from SOC stock of Slovenia $93.01\ t\ ha^{-1}$.

3.2. SOC stratification

SOC content decreased with increasing depth (Figure 1a; Supplementary material, Table S4). From the upper layer (0–10 cm) to the lowest layer (20–30 cm), the SOC content in CR was the least reduced by 15%, which is due to plowing, which usually reaches to a depth of approximately 25 cm and thus incorporates and evenly mixes organic residues and organic fertilizers into the 0–30 cm layer. In both VI and IO, the SOC stock in the 20–30 cm is reduced by 39% compared to the upper soil layer of 10 cm. In semi-natural ecosystems, there was a pronounced stratification of organic matter by 49%, 47%, 48%, and 47% in EO, GR, OG, and TB, respectively. This stratification is explained by the fact that organic matter, which enters the soil mainly through leaf fall

Figure 1. a) SOC stock (SOC), b) C in the fine fraction (C_{fine}), c) C saturation (C_{sat}) and d) C saturation deficit/surplus (C_{sd}) in t ha^{-1} by different depth layers (0–10, 10–20 and 20–30cm) and under different land uses. In boxplots, the left/right hinges correspond to Q_{25} and Q_{75} , the left/right whisker extends to the smallest/largest value no further than 1.5 times of interquartile range (Q_{25} – Q_{75}) from the left/right hinges, the + sign indicates the mean, the asterisk sign indicates outliers, and the grey circles show each sample sampled in years from 2016 to 2020. Land uses: CR – cropland, VI – vineyards, IO – intensive orchards, EO – extensive orchards, GR – grassland, OG – overgrown grassland, and TB – land with trees and bushes. Different letters indicate significant differences between different land uses and depths for SOC stock, C_{fine} , C_{sat} and C_{sd} at a probability of 0.05.

and the dense root system, accumulates in the upper horizons and reaches the deeper soil layers through natural, much slower processes such as bioturbation and leaching of organic material through macropores.

The actual SOC content in the fine fraction (C_{fine}) and the maximum predicted SOC content in the fine fraction (C_{sat}) also increased with depth (Figure 1b and c; Supplementary material, Table S6).

3.3. Fine soil fraction SOC deficit (Hassink's model)

The SOC in the fine fraction (C_{fine}) decreased with depth; although the content of the fine fraction

increased, the SOC stock decreased significantly with depth (SOC stratification) (Figure 1a and b). The calculations show that the lowest SOC content in the fine fraction (C_{fine}) was found on average in VI (20.8 in the upper 10cm and 48.7 t ha^{-1} as a sum in 0–30cm) and IO (22.5 and 52.9 t ha^{-1} , respectively), which is significantly less than that in other land uses and is probably due to deep ripping, that is deep tillage and lifting of the mineral subsoil into the surface layers of the soil in the preparation phase of intensive plantations. CR (26.3 and 73.5 t ha^{-1} respectively) and EO (31.1 and 67.8 t ha^{-1} respectively) contained more C_{fine} . GR (44.5 and 97.4 t ha^{-1}

respectively) and OG (45.7 and 100.8 t ha⁻¹ respectively) contain relatively high C_{fine} . The highest C_{fine} was found in TB (56.2 and 123.9 t ha⁻¹ respectively) (Supplementary material, Table S6).

In CR, the C_{fine} content was higher than that in VI and IO because the soil was plowed shallower (20–28 cm deep) and organic fertilizer in the form of animal manure is often added. Significantly higher C_{fine} content was found in soils that were less disturbed by tillage and had a higher input of organic matter.

From the difference between C_{fine} and C_{sat} we calculated the sequestration deficit of organic carbon in the fine soil fraction (C_{sd}), that is, the potential for sequestration of C in the fine soil fraction (SCS potential). A negative C_{sd} value indicates that there is already more carbon in the soil than the predicted sequestration of SOC in the fine fraction, which means that the soil has (over)reached the predicted amount of SOC in the fine fraction ($C_{\text{fine}} > C_{\text{sat}}$). In terms of the organic carbon (SOC) content, such soils are well supplied; therefore, it is important to maintain this condition. As expected, most samples from semi-natural land uses (EO, GR, and OG) had a negative potential or elevated SOC content above the saturation of the fine soil fraction. The majority of samples (>60%) with negative C_{sd} were found in the upper 10 cm, in the case of TB, even in 92% of samples, where the C_{fine} content was twice as high (100% higher) than C_{sat} . CR, on the other hand, exceeds C_{sat} in the upper 10 cm in only 28% of the samples and in 19% of the samples for the entire layer from 0 to 30 cm. As expected, VI and IO did not exceed the potential for C sequestration, as the soils on such agricultural land are most depleted in SOC owing to the intensity of cultivation and insufficient input of organic matter. On average, VI and IO (65.3 and 53.1 t ha⁻¹, respectively) and slightly less CR (39.2 t ha⁻¹) have the largest SOC deficits in the fine fraction at a depth of 0–30 cm.

In the upper 10 cm, EO had a small deficit of 8.4 t ha⁻¹, whereas GR, OG, and TB had the smallest deficits (6.7, 6.5 and 6.0 t ha⁻¹). These land uses also have the largest surplus of SOC, –11.0, –11.2, –17.7 and –21.5 respectively (Supplementary material, Table S6).

According to the calculated C_{sd} values for individual agricultural land uses, these values were also used to calculate the C_{sd} for all agricultural land in Slovenia (Table 2). We considered a depth of 0–30 cm and the average C_{sd} values (deficit and surplus).

The largest agricultural area in Slovenia is grassland (meadows and pastures) (347,223 ha; 17.1% of the total Slovenian area and 58% of the Slovenian

agricultural land, which occupies 601,108 ha), followed by cropland (179,003 ha; 8.8%) and other agricultural land uses with less than 35,000 ha (<2%) (Table 2). The total agricultural land use accounts for 31.3% of Slovenia's area, as shown in Figure S1 in Supplementary material. The potential to increase the SOC stock in the fine soil fraction (0–30 cm) is 16.3 Mt SOC for the whole country and 16.1 Mt SOC if we exclude TB and OG, which represent abandoned agricultural land in overgrowth where human intervention is no longer present and the fine soil fraction in these land uses is already supersaturated (TB) or nearly saturated (OG) (Table 2).

C_{fine} decreased with increasing depth (Figure 2). The C_{fine} values in the CR are not as variable in depth as in the GR, where significant stratification is observed. SOC for CR and GR appears to be higher with high clay content (>30%), especially in the upper 20 cm (not significant; $p=0.0517$). The C_{fine} on CR did not exceed the C_{sat} , which means that additional SOC could still be bound to a fine fraction in the cultivated areas, whereas in GR, the fine fraction was saturated in the upper 10 cm ($C_{\text{fine}} > C_{\text{sat}}$).

3.4. Soil management scenarios of possible soil carbon sequestration (SCS) potential rate (IPCC Tier 1)

For the calculation of SCS potential in Slovenia, we excluded land use TB because it was abandoned agricultural land and has now been in natural vegetation succession for many years without human intervention, and because the calculated fine fraction saturation potential of TB (C_{sd}) has already been reached or even exceeded (Table 2; Supplementary material, Table S6). Therefore, the SOC stock in the TB was used as a reference target value as C_{sat} for other land uses. The average SOC stock in agricultural land in Slovenia without TB is 93.01 t ha⁻¹ (0–30 cm), which means that on average we would need to sequester 0.37 t C ha⁻¹yr⁻¹ to reach the 4per1000 target.

When agricultural management of cropland would be conducted as usual over 20 years (intensive full tillage, low residue return, no cover crops; CR1) SOC stock decreases by 9.07 t C ha⁻¹. In CR2 (high input of residues, without the addition of manure), the SOC stock decreases by 5.70 t C ha⁻¹. Animal manure in addition to the high residue inputs (CR3) would increase SOC stock by 0.17 t C ha⁻¹. If we apply scenario CR3 on cropland and change the management of VI (VI2), IO (IO2) and

Figure 2. SOC stock in the fine fraction (<20 μ m) (C_{fine} - dark brown), SOC saturation of fine fraction (<20 μ m) (C_{sat} - light brown), and average measured SOC stock in soil (SOC T0 - black dot) in t ha⁻¹ depending on the different clay content (<20, 20–30, >30%) at 0–10, 10–20 and 20–30 cm depth in cropland (CR) and grassland (GR). Different letters in a row indicate significant differences between CR and GR in clay content and depth with a probability of 0.05.

Figure 3. Effect of land use scenarios on the change in SOC stock in 0–30cm. SOC stock at the time of sampling (T0 - dark shading), SOC stock after the use of different land use scenarios for 20years (scenario with light shading) and SOC stock of TB as reference (TB ref. - dark green) in t ha⁻¹ for different land uses in 0–30cm. Land uses: CR - cropland (brown colours), VI - vineyard (red colours), IO - intensive orchard (blue colours), EO - extensive orchard (grey colours), GR - grassland (green colours), OG - overgrown grassland (yellow colours), and TB - trees and bushes (dark green). The values for the SOC stock are based on the assumption that land use will not change in 20years (IPCC, 2019; Tier 1).

EO (EO2), where the rows are fully covered with grass turf, no deep tillage is applied and grass and pruning residues remain on the soil surface or are superficially incorporated into the soil, SOC stock increases by 2.11 t C ha⁻¹ (management scenario 4). If we change CR3 to CR4 where no-till is practised the SOC stock of all agricultural land uses increases by 4.67 t C ha⁻¹.

All management scenarios for agroecosystems described above (1–5) were considered grassland management remained unchanged (GR1). In the case of sustainable grassland management (GR2)

with light to moderate grazing pressure or cutting and at least one improvement (fertilization, species improvement, irrigation, liming), management scenario 6 significantly increases the SOC stock by 19.61 t C ha⁻¹.

The best management scenario was number 7, which considered in addition to the VI2, IO2, EO2, and GR2 scenarios, also conservation/regenerative agriculture (CR5) with no-till, high residue input, and high use of animal manure. Under these scenarios, the SOC stock increases by 24.1 t C ha⁻¹ in 20years or 1.2 t ha⁻¹yr⁻¹ (Table 3).

4. Discussion

4.1. SOC stock, stratification and fine soil fraction SOC deficit (Hassink's model)

The average SOC stock is highest in long-term abandoned areas overgrown by trees and bushes (TB), which can also serve as a reference for the highest achievable stock on Slovenian agricultural land (123.9 t ha⁻¹ in 0–30 cm). This is because of the annual input of organic material into the soil owing to the presence of deciduous trees and bushes with a dense plant canopy and a great diversity of species that cover the soil throughout the year, so that all residues remain and accumulate for years. As these soils are not cultivated, SOC mineralization is lower than that in cultivated areas (Chimento et al., 2016; Nadal-Romero et al., 2016; Novara et al., 2015). Overgrown grassland (OG) and secondary succession (TB) occur in Slovenia mainly at high altitudes, above 600 m a.s.l. (Cunder, 1999; Hočevár et al., 2004). On average, the temperature in Slovenia decreases by approximately 1°C by 180 m altitude elevation (Slovenian Environment Agency [SEA], 2018), what also contributes to higher organic matter content (Emde et al., 2022; Minasny et al., 2017; Wiesmeier et al., 2014).

All other land uses contained substantially lower SOC stocks compared to the reference value of 123.9 t ha⁻¹ in 0–30 cm, especially the intensively managed VI, IO, and CR by factors of 0.46, 0.42 and 0.30, respectively. Intensive tillage by plowing and additional tillage to prepare the soil bed and mechanical weeding disturb the soil layers every year and interrupt the process of stabilization of the SOC and accelerate its mineralization (Six et al., 1999) to such an extent that even the normal addition of organic fertilizer (e.g. 10 t ha⁻¹ of farmyard manure on an annual average in a crop rotation in mixed farms with livestock) (Kolmanič et al., 2021) cannot completely reverse the continuous SOC loss, for example, in scenario CR3, which is a common organic farming system (Mihelič et al., 2010). Tillage destroys soil structure, which in turn leads to the loss of occluded organic matter that is physically protected in structural aggregates (Rowley et al., 2018). By promoting soil aggregation through no-tillage or minimum tillage (IPCC management factor $F_{MG} = 1.10$) or by covering the soil with plant residues or living plants year-round (input factor $F_i = 1.44$) (IPCC, 2019), net C losses through decomposition processes are reduced (Bronick and Lal, 2005; Six et al., 2000; Tivet et al., 2013). Conventional tillage by plowing is a common practice in Slovenia; therefore, conversion to

conservation agriculture could increase C input to the soil and its preservation, but this can be observed only close to the surface (upper 10 cm) and not in the whole topsoil of 0–30 cm (Baker et al., 2007). In a compilation of existing data worldwide on zero tillage Baker et al. (2007) indicated that the carbon accumulation observed in the topsoil (0–30 cm) was in most cases compensated by losses in the subsoil (30–100 cm), which was further confirmed by the meta-papers by Luo et al. (2010), Ogle et al. (2019) and Liang et al. (2020). The implantation of cover-crops or catch crops to compensate the short growing cycles of cash crops has proven to almost systematically yield SOC stock recovery by an average 0.32 ± 0.08 t C ha⁻¹yr⁻¹ from 139 experiments worldwide considering the 0–20 cm layer (Poeplau and Don, 2015). However, Chaplot and Smith (2024) recently debated that cover crops may well increase SOC stocks in certain situations but it cannot be said for all pedo-climatic and agronomic conditions. They claim that nutrient availability in the soil is likely the most important limitation to organic matter formation and conservation into soils.

SCS rates are strongly influenced by annual temperature and precipitation (Wiesmeier et al., 2014), which means that the factors used in IPCC Tier 1 to calculate potential SCS are generalized. Two long-term experiments (LTE) were conducted in 1993 in two locations with different annual precipitation but with the same experimental treatments; one in Rakičan (807 mm precipitation, loamy-sandy soil) and the other in Jablje (moist region in central Slovenia, 1352 mm precipitation, loamy-silty soil). LTE treatments include crop rotation (grain maize, straw incorporation – winter wheat, straw removed – barley/oats, straw removed – oil reddish, whole crop incorporation) and regular application of farmyard manure (30 t ha⁻¹ every 3rd year) as well as moderate mineral nitrogen applications. Kolmanič et al. (2021) found that SOC stocks increased significantly (0.53 in Rakičan and 0.18 t SOC ha⁻¹yr⁻¹ in Jablje). These results are not consistent with the IPCC Tier 1 scenario CR3, which for such treatments predicted sequestration rate is close to zero (-0.03 t ha⁻¹yr⁻¹). Local long-term field experiments are therefore required to improve the model predictions. In the LTE in Moškanjci, Slovenia ('Rašica'; sandy-loamy soil, shallow Cambisol) from 2011 to 2020, the SOC stocks (t ha⁻¹) in the top 20 cm of the soil layer increased by 0.46 t ha⁻¹yr⁻¹ under minimum tillage compared to conventional tillage (Mihelič et al., 2024), which is consistent with scenario CR4. The supply of organic matter decreases when crop rotation does not

include cover crops, as C input is increased by dead roots, especially exudates from living plants and plant residues (Anuo et al., 2023; Maenhout et al., 2024; Poepflau and Don, 2015).

Vineyards (VI) showed the lowest SOC stock (66.7 t ha⁻¹, followed by IO (72.4 t ha⁻¹), which is well below the achievable stock (TB reference), well below CR (86.5 t ha⁻¹), which is a surprising result because most vineyards (VI) and intensive orchards (IO) in Slovenia are permanently covered by vegetation between rows, only approx. 1/3 of the soil surface in the rows of vines or trees is bare ('herbicide band'), where some superficial tillage is also carried out. The low SOC value in the 0–30 cm could have been caused mainly by heavy ameliorative plowing (70–90 cm) when the plantation was newly established. This brings the mineral subsoil to the surface (Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food [MAFF], 2016). Our results of C_{fine} confirm this. Only 42.7% and 49.9% of the fine soil fraction were saturated at VI and IO. In comparison, CR, which was intensively tilled by plowing, had a degree of saturation of 73.8%. Emde et al. (2022) stated that SOC content in the fine fraction can be increased and soil moisture can be better retained if herbicide use on the herbicide strip is restricted, soil amendments (e.g. organic mulches) or cover crops are used instead of limiting weed growth (Emde et al., 2022) and the optimal species mix is applied where development of living mulch under trees does not cause yield losses (Paušič et al., 2021). It would take more than 53 years for VI and 43 years for IO to reach saturation from C_{fine} . Even in the most regenerative scenario, EO2, which builds up the SOC by 1200 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, would take more than 29 years.

The situation is different for GR and EO, where agrotechnical work is not as intensive. The stocks of SOC were 12.6% and 7.4% larger than in CR, respectively. However, the stocks can be further increased or maintained through various measures: (i) renewing the turf without tillage; (ii) maximizing yields through moderate and technically justified fertilization; (iii) limiting the frequency of turf use by allowing plants to survive for a long time after each use through regeneration; and (iv) increasing the biotically diverse turf, including plants with a very deep root system (Chen et al., 2018b; Kramberger and Podvršnik, 2021).

The deficits (C_{sd}) are much lower in the upper 10 cm than in 10–30 cm. The C_{sd} in 0–10 cm is easier to reduce than in the entire depth of 0–30 cm. This is important for GR, EO and OG as organic matter is added to the soil annually by deciduous trees,

bushes, and grasslands. In addition, these areas are not cultivated and organic matter inputs are not mechanically incorporated deeper into the soil profile (Nicoloso et al., 2018), which means that mineralization is lower than that in cultivated areas. In addition, climate also contributes to higher organic matter content, especially the average annual temperature, which decreases with altitude (Cunder, 1999; Hočevár et al., 2004).

The opposite is true for cultivated soil. These soils are usually attributed to the breakdown of soil aggregates due to intensive tillage and the resulting loss of physically stabilized soil organic matter (labile form of SOC), reduced inputs from plants, including roots, and export of biomass (Post and Kwon, 2000; Six et al., 2000; Wiesmeier et al., 2014). Tivet et al. (2013) observed lower levels of mineral-associated organic carbon (C_{fine}) in continuously cultivated soil. In the areas that we currently intensively cultivate (CR, VI, and IO), C_{sd} is highest at 0–30 cm depth, in contrast to semi-natural and vegetated areas, as the SOC is mixed in depth. The causes of higher C_{sd} values are intensive agricultural practices (intensive tillage, mineral fertilization, and narrow crop rotation with low residue return) (Samson et al., 2020; Six et al., 2000).

The difference between the current SOC stock and SOC in fraction <20 μm (C_{fine}) is the amount of SOC in the coarse >20 μm fraction, which represents labile SOC (Besnard et al., 2001; Christensen, 1992; Hassink, 1997). SOC associated with a fraction >20 μm is a labile form of SOC that is not mineral-bound in the soil and usually increases in the top 10 cm of the soil. This labile fraction can be moved to deeper soil layers by tillage, especially by plowing (CR), whereas in GR, IO, VI, and semi-natural land use (TR, OG), movement to deeper soil layers is more restricted and slower, mainly by bioturbation and leaching (Briedis et al., 2023). In the conservation agriculture system, where we leave organic residues on the soil surface and where the soil layers are not mixed, a similar stratification of SOC is intentionally created, as for example, in grasslands (Figure 2).

We observed higher SOC contents in CR and GR with a higher clay content (>30%; Figure 3). This could be due to the increased physical protection of SOC by fine soil particles (von Lützow et al., 2006) and/or a lower decomposition rate of fresh organic matter and humification processes due to oxygen deficiency (Duchaufour, 1982; Nascimento et al., 2010).

Further analysis should verify whether soils with lower C_{sd} contain higher amounts of exchangeable divalent cations, such as Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺, which can

lead to direct sorption and inclusion of SOC into aggregates (Rowley et al., 218). Ca ions improve soil structure by mediating physico-chemical interactions between organic compounds and clay particles, thus physically protecting organic matter (occlusion) (Schweizer et al., 2021; Zhang and Norton, 2002).

In addition, the type of clay minerals present in the soil and the specific surface area with sorption capacity can have a major influence on the factors used to calculate C_{fine} and the saturation limit of the fine fraction (C_{sat}) (Georgiou et al., 2022; Steffens et al., 2009).

4.2. Soil management scenarios of possible soil carbon sequestration (SCS) potential rate (IPCC Tier 1)

Rodrigues et al. (2021) determined the SCS potential of mineral soils from croplands and grasslands under different soil management practices and land use in 14 European countries to be between 0.03 and 2.8‰ of the soil carbon stock. None of the countries investigated would reach the target of 4per1000 with current management practices. The same applies to agricultural soil use in Slovenia, where with the prevailing current agricultural land management (management scenario 3; Table 3) the SCS is almost balanced (+0.1‰). To reach the target of 4per1000 for the entire Slovenian agricultural land, a considerable amount of accumulated SOC would be required each year ($0.37 \text{ t ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$). However, such a pronounced accumulation of SOC requires a large annual external input of organic matter into intensive systems (CR, IO, VI) if the soil is plowed. This can only occur at the expense of transferring organic material from other agroecosystems, for example, through grass feed, purchased feed (cereals, soybeans), or litter (e.g. straw), which then indirectly enriches the fields in the form of organic fertilizer. The question is whether a high SOC accumulation rate is sustainable or not. A large net accumulation of organic matter accelerates biological processes in the soil, which can occasionally lead to excessive greenhouse gas emissions (N_2O and CH_4), an excess of nutrients (potassium, phosphorus, and nitrates), and increased environmental pollution (Maenhout et al., 2024).

In management scenario 4, where full tillage is still applied (scenario CR3 for cropland), grassland is managed with medium intensity and orchards and vineyards are fully covered with pruning residues and no deep tillage is applied between rows, the SOC stock should be increased by $0.11 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, i.e. by 1.14‰ of the average SOC stock in Slovenia. CR3

represents an established system of organic farming in Slovenia, which has a good crop rotation and uses animal manure, but involves intensive tillage including plowing and is therefore not able to significantly increase SOC stock on cultivated land; this was also shown by Leifeld and Fuhrer (2010) in a comprehensive review paper in which they reported that the benefits of organic farming for SOC are largely determined by a higher and often disproportionate use of organic fertilizer compared to conventional farming.

It appears that in subsoils, the SOC in fine fraction is the most important for sequestration processes. A larger proportion of the C in the subsoil is bound and stored in organo-mineral fractions and in fine pores. This form of carbon is stabilized and has a long turnover time. It is transported into the subsoil by plant roots and by leaching of dissolved organic matter (von Lützow et al., 2006). To increase the fine fraction C in the subsoil, plant species and varieties with deeper and thicker root systems are recommended to promote the activities of soil organisms and microorganisms in the subsoil (30–50 cm) (Button et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2018a). Chen et al. (2018a) showed that the SOC stock on the fine fraction in the subsoil is significantly lower than in the topsoil therefore the sequestration potential in the subsoil is significantly higher, regardless of land use.

In addition to the organic compounds adsorbed on the inner and outer surfaces of the mineral aggregates in the subsoil, free and occluded, label, organic compounds are also important (Briedis et al., 2023). Skadell et al. (2023) investigated the effects of different management practices (mineral nitrogen (N) fertilization, a combination of N, phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) fertilization, irrigation, a crop rotation with preceding crops (pre-crops), straw incorporation, application of farmyard manure, liming and reduced tillage) on SOC sequestration in mineral cropland soil (0–100 cm) in Germany. The influence of management practices on SOC stocks in the topsoil (0–30 cm) was greater than in the subsoil. The management effect in the topsoil amounted to 78.6%, in the subsoil (30–50 cm) 19% and in the subsoil (50–100 cm) only 3%. At a depth of 30–50 cm, nitrogen and NPK fertilization had the greatest influence on SOC sequestration, followed by irrigation, application of farmyard manure and incorporation of straw.

One of the management practices used to increase SOC in the subsoil is deep plowing, which is sometimes proposed as a method for enhancing SOC sequestration, the process of sequestering and storing carbon in soils by deep incorporation of

topsoil rich in soil organic matter (SOM), fresh residues and/or soil amendments (manure, compost), increasing the soil's depth and aeration (Burger et al., 2023; Shen et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2023). The long-term effectiveness and sustainability of deep tillage is questionable. The practice can lead to soil degradation, erosion, and disruption of soil ecosystems.

C sequestration is limited as C storage reaches equilibrium and the SCS potential rate decreases over time after the saturation point (Minasny et al., 2017; Rumpel et al., 2020). Minasny et al. (2017) have compiled an overview of studies on SOC experiences from 20 regions worldwide. Measured SOC sequestration rates indicate that an annual rate of 0.2 to 0.5 t C ha⁻¹ is possible when best management practices such as reduced tillage in combination with legume cover crops are applied. In addition, the binding of SOC at depths greater than 10 cm is limited, as SOC is found in the form of plant residues on the surface of extensively used agricultural land, including vineyards, intensive orchards and croplands with minimal tillage or no-till. In management practices that increase the SOC stock in the subsoil, we should also consider the preservation of the SOC that is already in the topsoil, as SOC stocks are sensitive to agro-technical measures (Chen et al., 2018a). Topsoil plowing is known to reduce SOC stocks (Six et al., 1999), and any equivalent or more physically disruptive practice should be better investigated before being put into practice.

A scenario 5 corresponds to conservation agriculture in CR, IO, EO and VI and increases SOC by 0.23 t ha⁻¹yr⁻¹, but still does not reach 4 per 1000 (0.37 t ha⁻¹yr⁻¹). For a further SOC increase that would exceed 4 per 1000 (0.98 t ha⁻¹yr⁻¹), in addition to conservation agriculture in the CR, the management of grassland should be changed to attain high sward biodiversity (scenario no. 6). The highest SCS potential rate would be difficult to achieve, but can be realized (scenario no. 7) if, in addition to the requirements of scenario no. 6, livestock is integrated into CR production by using the animal manure produced on the farm and/or by grazing on cropland. This also changes the feeding system of the livestock, which would be based more on the farm's produced feed, which can in turn affect the productivity of the animals and the economic results. Therefore, sustainable management of SOC ultimately leads to a change in agriculture as a whole. Further research should also investigate the economic and social aspects of the impact on the sustainability of the entire agricultural system, as well as the environmental aspects.

5. Conclusions

When calculating the sequestration potential of organic carbon into the fine soil fraction, we found that VI and IO had the highest deficit of organic carbon (50 – 57%), while CR and GR had similar and relatively low deficits (26%) compared to the reference TB (abandoned agricultural land overgrown with grassland, some trees, and bushes), which we considered as the maximum achievable SOC saturation. In CR and GR with a higher clay content (>30%), an increasing trend in SOC content was observed. Fine soil particles increase the physical protection of SOC and/or due to the increased oxygen deficiency, a lower decomposition rate of fresh organic matter and humification processes occur. Further analyses should verify whether these soils contain higher amounts of exchangeable divalent cations, such as Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺, which can lead to direct sorption and inclusion of SOC into aggregates.

Different management scenarios for agricultural land use in Slovenia showed that a fundamental change in management systems is needed for cropland (conservation agriculture, regenerative agriculture), vineyards and intensive orchards (permanent inter-row revegetation), and to a lesser extent for grassland in order to maintain soil quality and sequester C. Slovenian agricultural practices 'as usual' lead to a slow but steady decline of the SOC stock and an associated deterioration of soil quality.

In Slovenia, we could achieve an annual carbon sequestration of 2.5 per 1000 if we replace plowing with minimal soil disturbance and cover the soil surface not only in the CR, but also between the rows of trees and vines (conservation agriculture scenario). In this scenario, grassland management would be maintained as usual.

Organic farming in Slovenia, which has a good crop rotation and uses animal manure, cannot significantly increase the SOC stock on cropland due to intensive tillage, including plowing.

In addition to the introduction of cover crops, efficient fertilizer use and conservation agriculture, the integration of animal husbandry, which relies on feed produced on the farm, would lead to a significant increase in SOC content by 10–13 per 1000 (regenerative agriculture scenario). However, this would require a restructuring of the entire agricultural system toward a lower intensity and could lead to lower production, especially in livestock farming. This system change would also require investments in new machinery (for no-till systems) and other agricultural adaptations.

The results of this study can provide policy makers and farmers with insights into more environmentally

friendly and sustainable agricultural practices in Slovenia. Considering the current SOC stock and possible future SOC stock changes help to raise awareness of land use decisions and specific agricultural management practices. However, there are also some methodological limitations to consider. For calculation we used simple Tier 1 IPCC model, which considers only generalized data on climate and management factors, but not site-specific soil characteristics. Deterministic and geostatistical models using local long-term field experiments for calibrations are required to improve the model predictions and give more realistic results.

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Author contributions statement

Sara Mavsar: Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft, writing – review, and editing. **Helena Grčman:** Investigation, Validation. **Rok Turniški:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Validation. **Rok Mihelič:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft, writing – review, and editing. All authors have approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability statement

Raw data were generated at the Biotechnical Faculty of the University of Ljubljana, the Agricultural Institute of Slovenia and the Slovenian Forestry Institute. Derived data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author Rok Mihelič on request.

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